

CSR IMPLICATIONS TOWARDS QUALITY ENHANCEMENT THROUGH EFFECTIVE MARKETING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AMUL

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary business paradigm, companies cannot focus solely on monetary gains. They also need to include the dimension of social initiatives and emphasize on elevating the bottom line to boost the company image through good corporate citizenship. However, companies have now realized the relevance of Corporate Social Responsibility in the field of marketing for their short and long-term objectives. They have developed their own stronger marketing strategies around sustainability agendas for beating competitions and safeguarding their market position. As a result, today more than 90% of consumers say that they are more likely to buy from a company that supports and engages in the activities to improve society. The last half decade has witnessed a remarkable resurgence of attention among the practitioners and scholars to understand the ability of Corporate Social Responsibility to address environmental and social problems. "Corporate Social Responsibility is not about managing, reducing and avoiding the risk. It's about creating opportunity, generating improved sustainable profitable performance for people and planet".

In short, Corporate Social Responsibility is based on the three P's i.e., people, profit and planet which resolve around Social, Economic and Environmental development of the nation as a whole.

INTRODUCTION

CSR has been defined as the "commitment of business to contribute to sustainable economic development working with employees, their families, the local community and society at large to improve their quality of life, in ways that are both good for business and development."

AMUL is the Apex organization of the Dairy Cooperatives of Gujarat, popularly known as 'AMUL'. Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation (GCMMF) responsible for national and international marketing of milk and milk products produced and sold to it, The GCMMF is sensitive towards CSR. It believes that technology and capital are replicable inputs but not the human capital.

Today's world is globalized. It's a burden on the companies to sustain their own position in the market. With the introduction of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization, the whole world has become a single market which has increased the pressure on the companies, to market their own products by introducing themselves as a Corporate Leader with the concept of CSR. Today, companies are compelled to accommodate social activities in their marketing strategies so that they should be viewed as corporate citizens. Hence, they are now eagerly participating in environmental welfare along with implied economic prosperity. Companies have realised the relevance of CSR in marketing for their short term and long term objectives and accordingly they are developing stronger marketing

strategies around sustainability for beating the competitions and safe guarding their market position. This exhibits the companies concern and involvement in social and environmental issues in its business agenda. CSR efforts are linked more closely to the sub-brand or partnership than the company as a whole. It focuses on the marketing activities, its needs towards the target group. It co-operates to develop a sustainable effort that brings competitive advantage.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature will have focus on following aspects of consumer perception. The study tries to examine how CSR activities can excel the corporate reputation. It will have a primary focus on:

1. Understanding a Milk Federation, study of various product segments and profile of the Federation
2. Study of various marketing tools and techniques used by these industries for product promotion.
3. Study of various business strategies of leading brands in milk products. Focus will be on marketing and product promotion strategies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a) To understand the CSR role towards effective marketing.
- b) To analyse how effective marketing helps to improve quality.
- c) To analyse its implications on overall business.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Today entering into the global market has become inevitable in all the fields to lead with pride and ethics. The problem of the study focuses on how CSR can be affective and what will be its implications on the overall business development. This paper provides solution to this problem.

HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H0: Effective marketing of CSR will not have positive implications towards quality enhancement.

H1: Effective marketing of CSR will have positive implications towards quality enhancement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper based on the empirical research, techniques adopted and used for the study with the aim of achieving the research objectives. Data was collected from a sample of consumers surrounding Bangalore to determine the impact of CSR on them. However the study was restricted to Bangalore city primary data as well as secondary data which consist of items in well-structured and non-disguised questionnaire that was administered to and completed by the respondents. The respondents returned 500

questionnaires personally administrated. At the end the data was analysed with the help of chi-square.

Table: HYPOTHESIS (H0) CHI-SQUARE COMPUTATION

Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo-Fe) ² /Fe
65	55	10	100	1.82
45	55	-10	100	1.82
70	55	15	225	4.09
90	85	5	25	0.29
50	45	5	25	0.56
55	55	0	0	0
80	80	0	0	0
45	50	-5	25	0.5
			X ²	9.08

N/B

Degree of freedom = DF = 3

Significant Level = 0.05

Calculated X² = 9.08

Table – Value X² = 2.366

We reject H0 and accept the H1; hence to conclude we can say that Effective marketing of CSR will have positive implications towards quality enhancement.

FINDINGS& SUGGESTIONS:

The survey was conducted through a questionnaire which was distributed at shopping malls of different localities.

- Now customers are also smart enough, they know who is doing what and they also understand the importance of Corporate Social Responsibility.
- Around 90% of respondents are consuming milk products out of which majority share i.e. 56% goes to AMUL BRAND.
- Television has more influencing to grab more the buyer’s decision regarding the purchase of Amul products as we can see it advertises its products almost in all languages.
- Amul Product has more demand on special occasions.
- Even people are more enthusiastic for Amul’s Sugar Free Products if it is launched.
- We observed that Tag line of the product plays an important role in product promotion.
- It was found that CSR mechanism is becoming more popular. Even through analysis we can state that Amul have adopted CSR activities which can be seen through their vision & mission which would help to fulfil the CSR also.
- AMUL is doing innovation to find out some creative ways which may use lesser amount of resources to produce the same quantity of the products.

CONCLUSION:

- The AMUL Milk product brand has evolved into a Megabrand incorporating arrange of products each with their own identity.

- The strategy involved a packaging and range refreshment strategy which has resulted in a unified innovative Milk Products, Having exceeded initial sales targets by a considerable margin, the strategy can be considered a success.
- There is an immense scope for Milk Product Federation in India.
- Indian AMUL Federation is unique mix with extreme consumption patterns, attitudes, beliefs, income level and spending.
- Understanding consumer preferences and demands is the key to growth.
- Economical distribution using proper supply chain management is necessary.
- The Indian Milk Federation is destined to grow and will do so in the future.

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